

ANNOTATION GUIDELINE FOR FREE-TEXT ACTIVITY FUNCTIONING INFORMATION: MOBILITY

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1 INTRODUCTION

This work is a product of the Epidemiology and Biostatistics Section of the Rehabilitation Medicine Department, National Institutes of Health (NIH) Clinical Center that uses the International Classification of Functioning, Disability, and Health (ICF) (World Health Organization, 2001) as a framework for development of analytic tools for clinical natural language processing and vocabularies of function. The interdisciplinary team is intentionally composed of a diverse set of scientists, including those in health informatics, mathematics, statistics, computer science, public health, and healthcare. The annotation team that created this guideline included clinical rehabilitation domain experts with backgrounds in occupational therapy, physical therapy, primary care medicine, and individuals with public health and data science expertise.

Creation of the guideline was driven by a use case involving a collaborative agreement with the United States (U.S.) Social Security Administration (SSA) leveraging clinical natural language processing to improve the disability determination process. Its research purpose was to develop tools to automate detection of relevant functional information in electronic health records (EHR) in support of medical record review by adjudicators. This guideline aims to standardize mobility information documented in free-text EHRs and to provide a process for annotating this information. These efforts supported creation of a gold standard corpus, which has been used to develop computational models of functioning.

Use of the guideline

We recommend users of this guideline have a good understanding of mobility and domain expertise, or access to persons with domain expertise, that can clarify concepts and their semantic representation for annotation in clinical documentation. Though the guideline was developed for manual annotation, it can also be used to develop automated annotation tools for those interested in standardizing clinical documentation language of mobility.

This guideline provides a review of the ICF and how functioning at the activity level is conceptualized and identified for annotation. Familiarity with the ICF and its coding scheme is prerequisite. The ICF can be accessed through the [online ICF Browser](#), which outlines ICF categories with code names and descriptions. Users of the guideline need to be aware that the ICF is a working document and has ongoing updates which potentially add new codes or modifications to code name descriptions.

Appendices are provided as an additional resource for users of the guideline. [Appendix 1](#) lists the ICF mobility codes and definitions used in this guideline that were available at the time of annotation. [Appendix 2](#) provides a synthetic physical therapy evaluation and discharge note that has been annotated for mobility information. [Appendix 3](#) is a useful list of abbreviations that relate to mobility found in clinical documentation. Some ICF codes were challenging for

annotation due to being too broad, too specific, or having potential for 33 measures reported in this guideline.

Introduction to the ICF and conceptualization of function

The ICF was used as a framework to conceptualize functioning and standardize annotation of information at the activities level in EHR using clinical natural language processing (cNLP). The ICF was selected in view of its classification taxonomy of human functioning with world-wide adoption and providing standardized language of functioning concepts with codes and operational definitions. By establishing a common language for describing health and health-related states, the ICF has potential to improve communication between users, permit comparison of data across countries and disciplines, and provide a systematic coding scheme to be used by health information systems.

Functioning is classified on multiple levels, from body structures (e.g., cells and organs); to body functions (e.g., mental functions); and functioning at the level of activities and participation (e.g., self-care activities or work participation). An individual's functioning in a specific activity domain is understood as a complex relationship with dynamic interaction among a person's health condition, body structures and functions, and personal and environmental contextual factors (see Figure 1). Disability is understood as activity limitations or participation restrictions resulting from impairments or environmental barriers.

Figure 1: The ICF Scheme with the Activity component highlighted.

Functioning at the activity level is a salient health care outcome for both the individual and for population health (Bickenbach et al., 2023). Health is usually experienced by an individual as ability to participate in activities that one wants, needs, or is expected to do. Electronic health records are a rich source of functioning information. Clinical NLP (cNLP) has helped to extract

big data on human function for use in research that can evaluate intervention outcomes and inform health care policy to benefit individual and population health (Hasan & Farri, 2019). These cNLP efforts, however, have focused primarily on body functions and structures for medical decision support, such as diagnosing diseases and determining interventions (Bickenbach et al., 2023; Newman-Griffis et al., 2019). Extraction of functioning information at the activities level in EHR is much less represented and more challenging due to several factors, including a lack of standardization of clinical documentation among providers and inconsistent representation across health systems (Newman-Griffis et al., 2019).

As with all components in the ICF, the Activities and Participation component has several domains of functioning (see Figure 2). The ICF uses an alphanumeric system of coding in which the letters b, s, d, and e are used respectively to denote Body Functions, Body Structures, Activities and Participation, and Environmental Factors. These letters are followed by a numeric code that begins with the chapter number (one digit), followed by the second level (two digits), and the third and fourth levels (one digit each). Each functioning domain in the Activities and Participation component can be considered a parent category to subcategories nested within broader concepts. In the Activities and Participation component, codes can be added to denote qualifying constructs of capacity (the person’s ability to execute a task) and performance (the actual doing of the task). In addition, more than one code category can be applied to a particular function.

This guideline introduces annotation and coding of Mobility information at the activity level in support of cNLP efforts to automate information extraction in free-text EHR. All codes in the Activities and Participation domains begin with a “d.” As Mobility is the fourth chapter, it is coded “4.” Mobility codes begin with “d4” and are followed by numbers related to the sub-categories of mobility.

Figure 2: ICF Activities and Participation component highlighting the Mobility domain.

Conceptualizing Mobility

Mobility refers to a person's capacity to perform the physical act of moving the body for the purpose of engaging in activities the person wants to do, needs to do, or is expected to do. The ICF Mobility domain consists of activity codes that represent mobility activities, such as changing a body position or location, moving from one place to another, manipulating objects, or walking, running, climbing as well as using various forms of transportation (World Health Organization, 2001). ICF Mobility codes used for annotation are described generally below. Please see APPENDIXES 1: ICF Mobility Codes and Definitions for a complete table of ICF Mobility codes and their definitions as used in this guideline.

Changing and maintaining a body position (d410-d429) is part of movement in daily life that can include activities such as changing basic body positions (e.g., getting in and out of a sitting position such as getting up out of a chair), maintaining a body position (e.g., standing for some time as when waiting in line), and transferring oneself (e.g., using a sliding board to go from a wheelchair to a toilet).

Mobility also involves carrying, moving, and handling objects (d430-d449). This involves mobility actions of lifting and carrying objects (e.g., taking and carrying groceries from the car to the home), fine hand use (e.g., holding a pen), fine foot use (e.g., using the foot and toes to manipulate objects), and hand and arm use (e.g., reaching to put clothes in a washing machine).

Walking and moving (d450-d469) includes the act of walking in relationship to the environment (e.g., walking on different surfaces), moving around without walking (e.g., climbing or swimming), moving around in different locations (e.g., walking down the street in one's neighborhood), and moving around using adaptive equipment (e.g., using a mobility device such as a walker).

Community mobility includes moving around using transportation (d470-d489) and refers to using transportation as a passenger (e.g., taking the bus), driving some type of vehicle (e.g., driving a car or using a bicycle), or riding an animal for transportation (e.g., riding a horse).

2 ANNOTATION DATA

Data used for mobility annotation came from health records within the NIH Clinical Center. These records were provided by the NIH Biomedical Translational Research Information System (BTRIS), a resource available to the NIH intramural community, that provides records in limited data sets. The NIH Office of Human Subjects Research Protection (OHRP) determined that research conducted with these limited data sets does not meet the definition of human subjects research pursuant to 45 CFR 46 and OHRP guidance. The overall dataset consists of 577,735 clinical records (files) across 305 document names from 19,005 patients at the NIH Clinical Center. A document name refers to the discipline and type of note (e.g., Occupational Therapy Initial Assessment Note or Interim Note). A file refers to the actual note itself (the

individual assessment note). Domain experts filtered document names iteratively to narrow the dataset to documents containing information related to mobility. The final subset consisted of Physical Therapy (PT) Initial Assessment Notes, PT Reassessment Notes, PT Assessment and Discharge Notes, and other PT Notes. Domain experts then identified 1,954 files (orange shaded boxes) that were annotated for patients' mobility functional status (see Figure 3).

Figure 3: Annotation Data

3 ANNOTATION TOOL

A comprehensive review for available annotation tools was done in 2016-2017 and the General Architecture for Text Engineering (GATE) software tool (Cunningham et al., 2011) was selected due to its ease of use, portability, and customizable features that adequately met the needs of manual annotation and machine modelling. In addition, GATE did not require the data to be on a repository outside the NIH firewall and did not have a cost associated with open use. GATE is a general text processing framework that includes functionalities commonly found in typical NLP pipelines. While there are some disadvantages to this software, particularly in the realm of co-reference annotations, its utilities were sufficient to satisfy the annotation needs and purpose in creating this guideline.

4 ANNOTATION SCHEMA

Developing the Mobility annotation schema involved exploratory work by health professionals from varied backgrounds to identify components of mobility functional information in clinical free text. Once the major components of mobility (Mobility entity, Action sub-entity, Assistance sub-entity, and Quantification sub-entity) were determined, attributes and values to each of these components were added to provide additional contextual and/or functional information to the annotations. Annotators then tested the schema on a sample of documents and modified it according to information found in the text (i.e., the addition of the Score Definition and Instructions/Questions entities). Figure 4 shows the final framework of the schema.

Testing the schema was an iterative process between 2 human annotators using a quality assurance procedure aimed at achieving satisfactory inter-rater reliability (IRR). IRR of exact matching averaged 92.3 % F1-score on mention text spans, and 96.6 % Cohen's kappa on attributes assignments. Additional annotators provided input to refine the schema.

Figure 4: Mobility entity and sub-entities

The Mobility annotation schema, with its attributes and values, and the hierarchical coding structure are illustrated in Figure 5. Sequential steps of coding a mention of mobility information began with coding of mobility entities, followed by the entities' contextual attributes, then the attributes' values. Mobility mentions, entities, attributes, and values will be defined and described further in the next section.

Figure 5: Mobility Annotation Schema

4.1 Entities and Mentions

An entity refers to a concept of the information being annotated, and a mention is a textual statement of the underlying entity. In this guideline an entity is the description of what is annotated, and a mention refers to the text annotated.

Six entities make up the Mobility schema: Mobility; Action; Assistance; Quantification; Score Definition; and Instructions/Questions. The Action, Assistance, and Quantification entities are called Sub-entities, because they are part of the Mobility entity and always within it; the same naming structure applies to the Mentions. Definitions of all the entities and mentions are provided below.

A **Mobility entity** is a self-contained, well-defined description of physical functional status information. The definition is purposely broad to allow for normal textual variation of mobility documentation in clinical records. Three types of sub-entities may be present within a Mobility entity: Action, Assistance, and Quantification.

Action sub-entity refers to information about activities contained within the Mobility entity. An Action could be expressed as a verb or verb phrase, a noun or noun phrase, an inflection, a gerund, or a combination thereof. The key role of an Action entity is to identify the type of activity being done.

Assistance sub-entity refers to information about dependence on another person or object when performing an activity. The key role of an Assistance entity is to identify the level of practical support.

Quantification sub-entity is information related to measurement values of the activity.

Score Definition entity is a standardized assessment of functional status, commonly represented as numerical values that provide semantic interpretation of functional status. The Mobility entity and its sub-entities often refer to numerical values from a scale or as a score to quantify functional status. However, these scales are not part of a Mobility entity, and they are often defined separately in a series of short phrases. Score Definition is a standalone entity made up of short phrases that assist in the semantic interpretation of functional status.

Instructions/Questions entity refers to mobility information in the form of instructions and questions that contain no actual information related to the patient. Instructions for the provider about how to fill out a form related to the mobility of the patient or questions about mobility where no answer is given would fall into this category.

As explained above, a Mention is a textual statement that represents the instance of an underlying real-world entity. It is a contiguous span of tokens (a word or punctuation symbol) that makes up a phrase, a simple sentence, or a complex sentence.

Given that the Mobility entity contains three sub-entities (i.e., Action, Assistance, and Quantification), a Mobility mention may contain Action sub-mentions, Assistance sub-mentions, and Quantification sub-mentions. Figure 6 gives an example of a mobility mention and sub-mentions along with their linguistic roles.

Figure 6: Mobility mention and sub-mentions with their linguistic roles

As illustrated in Table 1, a specific color-coding scheme to identify mentions. The entire Mobility mention is highlighted in yellow, the text of the Action mention is blue, the text of the Assistance mention is red, the text of the Quantification mention is green, Score Definition mentions are highlighted in turquoise, and Instructions/questions mentions are highlighted in magenta. Please also refer to **Error! Reference source not found.** for an example of a clinical document fully annotated for the Mobility domain. Appendix 3 can also be used in conjunction as a resource of common abbreviations relating to mobility information found in clinical documentation.

Table 1: Color-coding legend for Mobility annotation

Color Scheme in GATE	Color Scheme in Guideline
Mobility	Yellow highlight
Action	Blue text
Assistance	Red text
Quantification	Green text
Score Definition	Turquoise highlight
Instructions/Questions	Magenta highlight

4.2 Attributes and Values

The Mobility entity, Action sub-entity, Assistance sub-entity, and Quantification sub-entity all have attribute coding possibilities. Score Definition and Instructions/Questions entities have no coding attributes. Attributes refer to a specific sub-type of mobility information and have Value codes. Value codes provide additional contextual and/or functional information about specific attributes and entities they are assigned to. Attributes and their Values for each of the Mobility, Action, Assistance, and Quantification entities and sub-entities are described below.

4.2.1 Mobility Entity: Attributes and Values

The Mobility Entity has three attributes: **Type**, **Subject** and **Timeline**. Attributes of the Mobility entity capture general information about functional mobility status. Each of these attributes has values and is further defined and described below.

The **Type** attribute refers to the source of the statement. If the statement is an observation from a clinical professional, the **Value** of the Type attribute is **Objective**. If the statement comes from a patient, a relative, etc., then the **Value** of the Type attribute is **Subjective**.

The **Subject** attribute refers to the person whom the statement is about. If the statement is about the patient, the **Value** of the Subject is **Patient**. Otherwise, the **Value** of the Subject is **Other**.

The **Timeline** attribute refers to when an activity occurred. If the activity in the mobility mention happened before the current health care visit, then the Timeline **Value** is **Past**. If the activity described is part of the current visit, then the Timeline **Value** is **Present**. If the activity is expected to occur after the visit, then the Timeline **Value** is **Future**. This **Future Value** is also assigned to statements that contain recommendations, goals, etc.

4.2.2 Action Sub-entity: Attributes and Values

The Action sub-entity has two attributes: **ICF Mobility Codes** and **Polarity**. Attributes of an Action entity capture the type of activity as well as a person's ability to perform the activity.

ICF Mobility Codes consist of thirteen 3-digit ICF Mobility codes that most closely represent mobility activities described in the text. In the annotation schema, ICF Mobility domain codes of "other specified" or "unspecified" in their descriptions were not included due to their ambiguity. Table 2 offers a detailed list of the 3-digit ICF codes, and their names used for Mobility annotation, along with text examples taken from EHRs. Please see APPENDIXES 1: ICF Mobility Codes and Definitions for a full description of the 3-digit ICF Mobility codes. These ICF Mobility codes were the codes published and available on the ICF browser at the time the guidelines were developed. The ICF continues to add codes on the online browser. ICF Mobility codes that are currently on the ICF Browser but were not so at the time of this guideline, and therefore not included here are: d446 Fine foot use; d451 Going up and down stairs; d465

Moving around using equipment. It is recommended that users check the [ICF online browser](#) for the most updated classification and codes.

Polarity refers to a person’s performance in an activity. If the person can do the activity, then the **Polarity** attribute of the Action entity is **Able**. If the person cannot do the activity, then the **Polarity** attribute of the Action entity is **Unable**. Otherwise, if the person’s ability cannot be assessed from the text (this includes effort, partially able, limited, impaired, and difficulty), the **Polarity** attribute of the Action entity is **Unclear**. If an activity is not performed or assessed, then the **Polarity** attribute of the Action entity is **No polarity**.

Table 2: Three-digit ICF Mobility codes

ICF Mobility Code	Mobility Code Name	Action Text Example
d410	Changing basic body position	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • She is independent with bed mobility supine to sit and sit to supine. • Sit to stand. • Squatting.
d415	Maintaining a body position	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • She is independent with sitting at the edge of bed (EOB). • Standing. • Pt was sitting in recliner while bed being changed.
d420	Transferring oneself	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Bed to chair/wheelchair.
d430	Lifting and carrying objects	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Loading and unloading groceries.
d435	Moving objects with lower extremities	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Kicking a ball. • Pushing pedals.
d440	Fine hand use	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Picking up. • Grasping.
d445	Hand and arm use	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Reaching to the cabinet. • Pulling a door closed.
d450	Walking	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Ambulation/Gait: Min Assist. • She walks without an assistive device (AD). • Patient demonstrated safe ambulation on level surfaces.
d455	Moving around	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Climbing the stairs. • Running. • Swimming.
d460	Moving around in different locations	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Walk to the bathroom*. • Wheel to the living room.

d465	Moving around using equipment**	
d470	Using transportation	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Riding the bus.
d475	Driving	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Ride a bike. • Drive a car.
d480	Riding animals for transportation	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Riding a horse.

*Use code “d460” to annotate “walking” when a destination is specified. Otherwise, use code “d450”.

Refer to APPENDIX 4: Troubleshooting Guide (Common terms and problems) to review the troubleshooting guideline as an additional resource for how ICF codes, particularly those to do with walking and moving, were operationalized for annotation.

** Code d465 was not used in this guideline as use of equipment was annotated as part of the Assistance mention.

4.2.3 Assistance Sub-entity: Attributes and Values

The Assistance sub-entity has two attributes: **Polarity** and **Source**. These attributes capture the general level and type of help or support the patient requires to complete an activity.

Polarity refers to the level of help/support a person needs to complete an activity. The word “dependence” is used to note the need for some type of help/support. If a person does require help, the value of the **polarity** attribute is **true (dependent)**. If the person does not require help, then the value of the **polarity** attribute is **false (independent)**. If the level of dependence cannot be assessed from the text, the value of the **polarity** attribute is **unclear**. If the assistance is for future use (e.g., goals or recommendations), then the value of the **polarity** attribute is **no polarity**.

Source refers to the type of support a person requires to complete an activity. If the support is an assistive device such as a walker, cane, or wheelchair, then the Value of the **source** attribute is **device**. If another individual is helping a person complete the activity, such as through supervision or contact guard assist, then the Value of the **source** attribute is **person**. Otherwise, if the person relies on other types of assistance, such as objects in the environment, the value of the **source** attribute is **‘other.’** This refers to mobility aids in the environment (e.g., stair railings and bed rails) that are not intended for long-term use (e.g., an IV pole) or worn to aid mobility, such as a knee brace. If the type of support is for future use, then the value of the Source attribute is **no source**.

4.2.4 Quantification Sub-entity: Attributes and Values

Type is the single attribute of the Quantification sub-entity and refers to what is being measured. The values of the Quantification attribute are distance, time, scale, frequency, and

other. **Distance** values refer to measurable lengths of mobility activity. **Time** values refer to measurable temporal durations. The **Scale** value refers to any number representing a patient’s mobility score. **Frequency** is assigned as a value if the activity occurs or is repeated over a specified interval. **Other** quantification values include measures other than distance, time, scale, or frequency, such as weight, height, or speed (e.g., miles per hour for walking on a treadmill).

5 GENERAL CONSIDERATIONS

Annotating a Mobility mention and its sub-mentions can be carried out in many ways. It is recommended that annotators approach the task in a top-down fashion: first apply general rules, then apply rules specific to the entity type.

To annotate a health record, an annotator first identifies Mobility mentions, followed by sub-mentions (Action, Assistance, Quantification) within each Mobility mention. For each mention or sub-mention, the annotator assigns a value to corresponding attributes. Examples of these values are type=subjective (Mobility mention), source=device (Assistance mention), and polarity=able (Action mention).

Score Definition mentions are identified separately from Mobility mentions and do not contain any sub-mentions or attributes. See Figure 7 that illustrates the annotation workflow process.

Figure 7: Workflow of mobility annotation

5.1 Misspelling and over-redaction

Misspellings and over-redactions do occur in clinical documents. For annotation, do not edit texts in the health records. If an annotator can understand the text as written, and it contains mobility functional information, then it should be annotated. Below are some examples.

Typographical error example: She walkswith a cane

With run-on words, only the text of interest is annotated. In the example above, if we were capturing action mentions, only the word “walks” would be annotated.

Over-redaction example: rolling [LAST NAME = 0000]

Annotate “rolling [LAST NAME = 0000]” as it is **without** replacing redacted information (e.g. [LAST_NAME=0000] with “walker”).

Misspelling example: Transfer form bed-chair

Annotate “transfer form bed-chair” as it is without changing “form” to “from”.

5.2 General Guidelines for Annotating Mentions

1. Annotate only mobility information from the clinical records. That is, annotate patient mobility status, whether in phrases or sentences.
2. Do not include punctuation at the beginning or end of a mention; if possible, just annotate the shortest span of text.

Example 1: Pt walks 120' with wheeled walker and CGA.

Example 2: Pt states, “I can walk with a cane.”

Example 3: Pt walks 120' (with wheeled walker and CGA).

3. There is a sequence to annotation. Annotate each Mobility mention first, and then annotate sub-mentions (Action, Assistance, and Quantification) within each Mobility mention. Sub-mentions never exist outside a Mobility mention.

Example 1: Pt walks 120' with wheeled walker and CGA

- a. Annotate Mobility mention: Pt walks 120' with wheeled walker and CGA.

- b. Then annotate Action mention: Pt walks 120' with wheeled walker and CGA.
 - c. Then annotate Assistance mention: Pt walks 120' with wheeled walker and CGA.
 - d. Then annotate Quantification mention: Pt walks 120' with wheeled walker and CGA.
4. A Mobility mention can contain one or more sub-mentions.

Example1: Able to maintain static standing balance (Just Action mention)

Example2: She does not require the use of an assistive device (Just Assistance mention)

Example3: Patient independent with sit to stand (Contains both Action and Assistance mentions)

5. A Mobility mention can contain the same type of sub-mention multiple times.

Example1: Sit to stand/ stand to sit: CGA/ min A

This Mobility mention has two Action mentions – “sit to stand” and “stand to sit” – and two Assistance mentions – “CGA” and “min A”.

Example2: Patient able to demo bed mobility, transfers and ambulation

This Mobility mention contains three Action mentions – “bed mobility”, “transfer”, and “ambulation”.

6. Two sub-mentions within a Mobility mention can overlap.

Example1: Patient can walk with cane around the room

The Action mention “walk with cane around the room” overlaps with Assistance mention “with cane.”

7. Mobility mentions never overlap.

8. Score Definition mentions never overlap with each other or with Mobility mentions.

9. Each Mobility mention and sub-mention should be as specific as possible, which may require capturing a longer span of tokens while restricting it to the shortest span of tokens that still preserves the entity's meaning.

Example1: Pt will transition sit-stand from chair/bed with SBA.

In this Mobility mention, the phrase "sit-stand" is enough to assign an ICF code, but the longer phrase "transition sit-stand from chair/bed" better describes the specific type of activity, and so it will be annotated as the Action mention. However, the word "will" is excluded since its presence does not affect the meaning of the Action phrase.

Example2: Able to transition sit-stand.

In this Mobility mention, the phrase "sit-stand" suffices as an Action, but "transition" is included to make the Action more specific. However, "able to" is excluded to make the Action more compact, and ability is instead captured via the Polarity attribute.

Example3: Gait instability and numbness and tingling in the hands.

In this example, the Mobility mention is the shortest span of text that conveys an atomic (unbreakable) piece of functional mobility information.

5.2.1 General Guidelines for Attributes and Values

1. Some attributes are required, and others are optional. See the Attribute-specific guidelines for details.
2. Assign an attribute to a mention only when information is explicitly stated in the text.
 - 2.1. Assistance mention attribute examples:

Example 1: The patient can walk independently. [polarity=false, source=no source]

The Assistance mention has a polarity of false with a no source attribute.

Example 2: The patient can walk independently without the use of a rolling walker. [polarity=false, source=device]

The Assistance mention has both polarity (false) and source (device) attributes.

Example 3: The patient would benefit from the use of a walker for ambulation. [polarity= no polarity, source=device]

The Assistance mention has no polarity but does have a source attribute (device) because this is a hypothetical statement.

2.2. Action mention attributes examples:

Example 1: Can walk short distances without assistive device. [subdomain code=d450, polarity=able]

The Action mention has a Polarity of “able” and an ICF Mobility subdomain code (d450) because it is implied that the action is being performed by the patient.

Example 2: My main goal is to improve walking with less risk of falling. [subdomain code=d450, polarity=no polarity]

The Action mention has no polarity because it is part of a goal statement, i.e., it was not performed, but it still has an ICF Mobility subdomain code (d450).

3. Attributes are independent; the value of one attribute does not depend on the value of another.

Example 1: Patient is able to ambulate in the hallway without a rolling walker. [action polarity=able, assistance polarity=false]

The polarity of the Action mention (“ambulate in the hallway”) is “able.” The polarity of the Assistance mention (“without a rolling walker”) is false.

4. If mobility related functioning is “not assessed,” then annotate it as a Mobility mention and annotate any Action or Assistance sub-mentions without a polarity attribute (polarity=no polarity).

Example1: Chair/wheelchair to bed: not assessed. [polarity=no polarity]

The Action mention “chair/wheelchair to bed” has no polarity.

Example2: Wheelchair: not assessed. [polarity=no polarity]

The Assistance mention “Wheelchair” has no polarity.

5. Attributes convey important information relevant to the mobility entity. Thus, values assigned to attributes should be derived from the holistic meaning of the Mobility entity, not limited to local syntactical structure.

Example 1: Unable to propel wheelchair independently. [polarity=unclear]

The Action mention “propel” has a polarity of “unclear” because the cue word “unable” modifies the Assistance mention “unable to propel wheelchair independently.” While the text states that the patient cannot propel the wheelchair independently, there is no

information on the patient's ability with additional assistance, and so the overall polarity is unclear.

Example 2: The patient is independent without the use of assistive device except requiring a walker for long distance ambulation. [polarity=true, source=device]

The Assistance mention has a Polarity of true and a Source of device

6 MOBILITY SPECIFIC CONSIDERATIONS

6.1 Mobility Entity

1. A complex, long sentence related to mobility functional information could have multiple clauses with conjunctions. If separating its clauses into distinct Mobility entities allows them to stand on their own and still make sense, then annotate these clauses as multiple Mobility entities, even though they share the same subject.

Example 1: “We saw him walk on level with front wheeled walker with CG Assist, transfer to and from chair independently, utilize a roll-a-bout for approximately 25-30 minutes with several turns to the L side only, as instructed, and transfer to and from chair and mat table from roll-a-bout and standard front wheeled walker all with close supervision.”

The following sentence is divided into three separate mobility entities.

“We saw him walk on level with front wheeled walker with CG Assist, transfer to and from chair independently,

utilize a roll-a-bout for approximately 25-30 minutes with several turns to the L side only, as instructed, and

transfer to and from chair and mat table from roll-a-bout and standard front wheeled walker all with close supervision.”

2. On the other hand, combine multiple phrases to form a single Mobility mention when they are related and separately cannot stand on their own. For example, the following is a single Mobility mention since all the phrases relate to the “Ambulation/Gait” header.

Example 1: Ambulation/Gait: Level of assistance: Supervision Assistive device: Cane Distance: 150ft Type of surface: Level

3. Only annotate headers, titles, and generic programs (e.g., bed mobility training, bed mobility skills, walking program, climbing pattern, gait pattern, dynamic sitting balance, and static standing balance) when there is no Action information in the following text. Do not annotate headers, titles, and generic programs when the following text contains

Action information. See Table 3 for examples of when and when not to include headers in annotation.

Table 3: Annotation of Headers and Titles.

AMB: 15-50 ft w/ platform walker and min-Mod assist.	AMB: AMB 15-50 ft w/ platform walker and min-Mod assist. Bed mobility: Rolling: Independent.
Ambulation/gait: independent.	Ambulation/gait: pt ambulated in the room. Transfer: sit to stand: Independent.
Examples of annotated header/title	Example of header/title that is not annotated
Gait pattern: mild ataxia, decreased step/stride length, decrease velocity. Chair/wheelchair to bed: not assessed.	Gait pattern: abnormal gait. Gait: Supervised to ambulate 100 w/RW.

- When an Assistance mention is the only sub-mention present within a Mobility mention, annotate the context or heading as part of the Mobility mention, as it provides information about the type of mobility functioning where assistance is need.

Example 1: Supine to sit: Moderate Assist

- Annotate sentences as Mobility mentions when patient uses an assistive device (e.g., crutches) for ambulation even when “ambulation” or an equivalent term is not explicitly stated.

Example 1: Patient demonstrated safe use of crutches.

Example 2: Pt currently prefers to use a cane.

Example 3: She can also use the rolling front-wheeled walker.

- In parts of the document where there is a question and an answer, annotate the span of text as a Mobility mention with all the sub-mentions, attributes, and values as in the example below.

Example 1: Does the patient have the ability to transfer from the bed to the chair? YES

These annotations where a question has an answer (meaning the patient was evaluated or they are performing an action) differ from annotating only questions that contain Mobility information but are not related to the patient (which are annotated with the Instructions/Questions mention) as the guideline shows in [section 6.6](#)

6.1.1 Attributes and Values of the Mobility Entity

The Mobility entity has three attributes: Type, Subject, and Timeline. All three attributes are required, i.e., they must be assigned values.

1. Examples of the **Type attribute** with the corresponding value in square brackets.

Example 1: Patient demonstrated safe ambulation up/down 4-6 steps using rail. [type=objective]

Example 2: She reports being independent with functional mobility and ADLs without the need for assistive device. [type=subjective]

2. Examples of the **Subject attribute** with the corresponding value in square brackets.

Example 1: She is independent with ambulation w/o the use of an assistive device. [subject=patient]

Example 2: Her cousin is also wheelchair bound and requires assistance with all bed mobility. [subject=other]

3. Examples of the **Timeline attribute** with the corresponding value in square brackets:

Example 1: She was independent with functional mobility prior to admit. [timeline=past]

Example 2: She is independent with bed mobility supine to sit and sit to supine. [timeline=present]

Example 3: Patient will ambulate >100 ft. with rw and supervision. [timeline=future]

Example 4: Recommendation to patient: use cane for community ambulation. [timeline=future]

6.2 Action Entity

Captures local modifiers as part of the Action mention related to ICF codes.

1. Do not annotate local modifiers of the Action mention, such as “able to,” “unable to,” “should,” “shouldn’t,” etc. since the primary role of an Action mention is to capture the type of activity. The information provided by the local modifiers is captured instead via the Polarity attribute.

Example 1: Only the phrase “walk up the stairs” is annotated as the Action mention. Patient able to walk up the stairs.

2. An Action mention can cover an entire Mobility mention.

Examples 1: Supine <-> edge of bed (EOB) sit.
Example 2: Transfer in and out of bed to chair.

3. When multiple actions are listed in a hierarchical fashion, only annotate the most specific one as the Action mention.

Example 1: Locomotion/mobility/gait: impaired

6.2.1 Attributes and Values of the Action Entity

The Action entity has two attributes: subdomain codes and polarity. The subdomain code corresponds to the ICF Mobility codes in Table 2. The polarity code corresponds to a person's ability to perform an action (able, unable, unclear, or no polarity).

1. Examples of the subdomain code **attribute** with the corresponding code in square brackets:

Example 1: She is independent with bed mobility. [subdomain code=d410]

Example 2: She is able to move from sit on a raised surface to stand with min A without a.d. [subdomain code=d410]

Example 3: She requires min A to maintain safe standing without a.d. [subdomain code=d415]

Example 4: She is independent with sitting at the EOB. [subdomain code=d415]

2. Examples of the polarity attribute with the corresponding value in square brackets:

Example 1: She is independent with bed mobility. [polarity=able]

Example 2: Patient unable to perform sit to stand. [polarity=unable]

Example 3: She has difficulty transferring to stand up. [polarity=unclear]

3. Use "no code" for subdomain code if the Action mention cannot be matched to an ICF mobility code. Use "no polarity" for activities that are not performed or assessed (e.g., goals).

Example 1: Unable to propel wheelchair independently. [subdomain code=no code]

Example 2: Pt is able to march in place. [subdomain code=no code]

Example 3: She will walk twice a day. [polarity=no polarity]

Example 4: He would benefit from using a cane for ambulation. [polarity= no polarity]

The terms “propel” and “march in place” can refer to different types of actions and cannot be summarized with a single discrete ICF code. Thus, the subdomain code is “no code.”

6.2.2 Special annotation cases related to Action mentions

6.2.2.1 Do not annotate Action mentions when an activity is not explicitly stated.

Example 1: He states he was able to do this independently prior to his surgery but now needs to elevate the bed some to assist with getting up.

Do not annotate “do this” as an Action mention.

6.2.2.2 If an activity does not have a matching ICF Mobility code, assign “no code” as its subdomain code. Do not infer a code for an activity that is vague and does not have a matching ICF code.

Example 1: She must negotiate steps. [subdomain code=no code; polarity=able]

In this example, do not infer “negotiate steps” is the same as “climb stairs,” for the former does not explicitly state how the person goes up and down stairs (e.g., crawling, climbing). Since there are no ICF codes that describe “negotiate,” the subdomain code is “no code.”

6.2.2.3 When the mention denotes more than one type of activity, select “no code” for subdomain code.

Example 1: Pt is able to ambulate in the hallway and stairs. [subdomain code=no code; polarity=able]

The Action mention “ambulate in the hallway and stairs” refers to two different activities: walking (subdomain code= d450) and climbing (subdomain code= d455).

Example 2: Pt does walk for 30 minutes on the treadmill at 3 mph, and 45 minutes around her neighborhood. [subdomain code=no code; polarity=able]

The action mention “walk for 30 minutes on the treadmill at 3 mph, and 45 minutes around her neighborhood” is used to describe both walking on the treadmill (subdomain code= d450) and walking around the neighborhood (subdomain code=d460).

6.2.2.4 *Annotate an Action mention with a single ICF Mobility Code when it is used for the same ICF activity performed multiple times.*

Example 1: pt can ambulate within the home and to the grocery store. [subdomain code=d460; polarity=able]

The Action mention “ambulate within the home and to the grocery store” is used for both activities of moving around (subdomain code=d460).

6.2.2.5 *Use “no polarity” when an Action mention is part of a Future Mobility mention (e.g., Patient goals, Physical therapy goals, Recommendations, etc.), rating scale, and when the action is not performed or evaluated due to lack of information about ability to perform the activity.*

Example 1: ambulation: 4 (rating or scale)

Example 2: patient will ambulate 400 ft in 1 week. (future occurrence)

Example 3: Patient does not want to ambulate today. (activity not performed)

6.2.2.6 *Action mentions that are expected to happen in the future (e.g., will, will not, could, should, would, could not, should not, and would not) have an ICF Mobility Code but no Polarity.*

Example 1: I would like to walk without an assistive device. [subdomain code=d450; polarity=no polarity]

Example 2: Patient should walk with an assistive device. subdomain code=d450; polarity=no polarity]

Example 3: Patient should avoid ambulating without a cane. [subdomain code=d450; polarity=no polarity]

Example 4: Patient should not ride a bike. [subdomain code=d475; polarity=no polarity]

6.2.2.7 *Leave the Polarity for an Action mention as “no polarity” when the ability of performing an activity is not explicitly stated or assessed.*

Example 1: He avoids use of stairs. [subdomain code=d455; polarity=no polarity]

Example 2: He does not run and never goes up more than 2 flights of steps.

“run” [subdomain code=d455; polarity=no polarity]

“Goes up more than 2 flights of steps” [subdomain code=d455; polarity=no polarity]

6.2.2.8 *Leave the Polarity for an Action mention as “no polarity” when it is related to treatment, interventions, education, or therapeutic services and does not explicitly denote patient’s ability or performance.*

Example 1: Patient received gait training. [subdomain code=d450; polarity=no polarity]

6.3 Assistance Entity

Captures local modifiers as part of the Assistance mention to indicate level of dependence.

Example 1: She does not require the use of an assistive device.

6.3.1 Attributes and Values of the Assistance Entity

The Assistance entity has two attributes: **Polarity** and **Source**. Both attributes are optional, i.e., they do not have to be assigned a value.

Polarity has four Values: true (Dependent); false (Independent); unclear, and no polarity.

Source has four Values: device; person; other, and no source.

The following are some examples of Mobility mentions highlighted in yellow, with the Assistance entity highlighted in red font, followed by assistance Values in square brackets.

Do not annotate assistance mentions when talking about something that the patient owns or has at home (e.g., The patient has a rolling walker at home), this is NOT an assistance mention as the patient is not using them.

Assistance: Polarity attribute and values examples:

Example 1: She requires min A to maintain safe standing. [polarity=true (dependent)]

Example 2: She is independent with sitting at the EOB. [polarity=false (independent)]

Example 3: With or without assistive device [polarity=unclear]

Example 4: He would need a cane to walk outside the house [polarity=no polarity]

Note: In the following example, the value of the Polarity attribute depends on the context. The Polarity of the following Assistance mention is True (Dependent) because the meaning is that the person would require assistance to propel their wheelchair.

Example 5: Unable to propel wheelchair independently. [polarity=true]

Assistance: Source attribute and values examples:

Note: An Assistance mention of “Independent” or “Independence” is assigned a Source attribute of “no source,” since Source is only assigned if the need and/or type of assistance is identified.

Example 1: Ambulation with single point cane for longer distances. [source=device]

Example 2: Transfer: Modified independent sit-to-stand [source=device]

Example 3: Bed to chair: Modified independent [source=device]

Example 4: Supine to sit: Moderate Assist [source=person]

Example 5: Pt will transition sit-stand from chair/bed with SBA [source=person]

Example 7: Patient will ascend/descend at least 2 steps with CGA from her husband. [source=person]

Example 8: Supine to sit: Moderate Assist [source=person]

Example 9: Up/down 4 steps with 1 rail [source=other]

Example 10: Patient able to negotiate stairs using rails. [source=other]

Example 11: Patient is able to ambulate with the help of IV pole. [source=other]

Example 12: She is independent with sitting at the EOB. [source=no source]

1. When an Assistance mention is the only sub-mention present within a Mobility mention, annotate the context or heading as part of the Mobility mention, even though it may not provide functional information.

Example 1: Supine to sit: Moderate Assist [source=person]

2. Assistance entities with the following terms are assigned Polarity=**true**, and Source=**person**:

- Total assistance (or total assist)
- Maximal assistance (or Max assist)
- Moderate assistance (or Mod assist)
- Minimal assistance (or Min assist)
- Contact guard assist
- Supervision
- Prompting
- Cueing
- Relying on staff
- Encouragement of staff
- Needs help

3. Assistance entities with the following terms are assigned Polarity=**true**, but the Source should be “**no source**” because it is too vague:

- Dependent
- With assistance
- Assistance needed
- Assist
- With assist
- Assist needed

4. Assistance entities with the following terms are assigned Source=**device**:

- Canes
- Crutches
- long-handled reachers
- walkers
- Wheelchairs

5. Assistance entities including, but not limited to, the following terms are assigned a Source=**other**:

- Adaptive devices (e.g., elevated/raised head of bed, raised toilet seats)
- Braces
- Orthotic and prosthetic devices
- IV pole
- Arms of chair

6. When “with” and “without” are used for more than one Assistance mention, annotate the **polarity** according to the context.

Example 1: He has surpassed all of his goals and is now ambulating on level surfaces and up and down steps **without an assistive device** or **using rails** as tolerated.

While the Assistance mention “using rails” does not contain the word “without,” Polarity is annotated as “false” based on the context.

Annotation 1: “**without an assistive device**” [polarity=false; source=device]

Annotation 2: “**using rails**” [polarity=false; source=other]

7. When the word “Independent” is used for more than one Assistance mention that could be classified under different “Source” attributes, annotate the whole phrase as the assistance mention with **Polarity**=True, and **Source**=no source.

Example 1: independent community ambulation with O2 and rolling walker
[polarity=true; source=no source]

The assistance mention above starts with the word “independent,” and this word applies to both “O2” and “rolling walker.” Both mentions have different “Source” attributes (“other” and “device,” respectively). To capture the information more accurately, select the whole phrase as the assistance mention with a “polarity” attribute of “true” and the “source” attribute of “no source.” Note that ‘no source’ indicates the presence of multiple assistance sources (e.g., oxygen and a rolling walker), not the absence of any assistance.

8. If the word “independent” is associated with a specific Source (person, device, other), annotate them together to capture the polarity accurately.

Example 1: Patient is independent with assistive device. [source=device, polarity=true]

Example 2: Patient is independent without assistive device [source = device, polarity = false]

Example 3: Patient is Independent with assist. [source=person, polarity=true]

9. When an Assistance mention is part of a Future Mobility mention (e.g., Patient Goals, Physical Therapy Goals, Recommendations, etc.), use “no polarity” for Polarity attribute.

Assistance mentions that are expected to happen in the future (e.g., will, will not, could, should, would, could not, should not, and would not) have a Source attribute but no Polarity. Since Polarity is coded “no polarity” for future Assistance mentions, only annotate the Source. **The following examples illustrate the difference between setting Timeline to “future” versus “present” for the same assistance mention.**

Example 1:

(Future): I would like to walk without an assistive device. [source=device; polarity=no polarity]

(Present): Patient walks without an assistive device. [source=device; polarity=false]

Example 2:

(Future): Patient could benefit from using handrail when climbing stairs. [source=other; polarity=no polarity]

(Present): Patient uses handrail when climbing stairs. [source=othe,, polarity=true]

Example 3:

(Future): Patient would benefit of Min A for sit to stand transitions. [source=person; polarity=no polarity]

(Present): Patient requires Min A for sit to stand transitions. [source=person; polarity=true]

10. When an Assistance mention is part of a Future Mobility mention and only contains the word “Independent” or “Independence,” use no polarity and no source attributes.

Example 1: Patient will be independent in all transfers. [source=no source; polarity=no polarity]

Example 2: Patient will be independent [source=no source; polarity=no polarity] with rolling walker. [source=device; polarity=no polarity]

6.4 Quantification Entity

Captures local modifiers such as adjectives, adverbs, mathematical operators, and units as part of the Quantification mention.

Example 1: Patient will ambulate >100 ft. with rw and supervision.

Example 2: Patient demonstrates safe ambulation for approximately 100 ft.

6.4.1 Attributes and values of the Quantification Entity

The Quantification entity contains a single attribute, “Type”, which is required and cannot be left blank.

Examples of the Type attribute with the corresponding value in square brackets:

Example 1: Patient will ambulate >100 ft. with rw and supervision. [type=distance]

Example 2: Patient ambulated 8 steps up the stairs. [type=distance]

Example 3: Swim daily. [type=frequency]

Example 4: Patient will be seen 3x a week for gait training. [type=frequency]

Example 5: Walk 1-2 miles x3/day [type=distance; type=frequency]

Example 6: Her heel pain worsens after prolonged walking and can reach 10/10 when walking > 1 hr. [type=time]

Example 7: Transfer score: 4 [type=scale]

Example 8: He can walk for 30 minutes at 3 miles an hour on the treadmill.

30 minutes [type=time]

at 3 miles an hour [type=other]

Note: Quantification mentions with a specified time during the day, week, etc., are annotated together as ONE frequency mention.

Example 1: Patient will ambulate 3-4 hours daily. [type=frequency]

Example 2: Patient ambulated 3 hours a day. [type=frequency]

6.5 Score Definition Entity

The Score Definition entity is a score or scale captured in Quantification entities. Score Definition is a unique entity and as such is annotated separately from Mobility entities and their sub-entities. Annotate the Score Definition at its first occurrence in the text. The following is an example of a Score Definition mention.

Example 1:

Mobility: -Scoring: 1-4; 1=Total dependent 2= requires assistance of a person (with or without appliance), 3= requires appliances, orthosis or prosthesis for independence, 4= totally independent (indoors/outdoors)

6.6 Instructions/Questions Entity

The Instructions/Questions entity contains mobility information in the form of instructions and questions where there is no actual information related to the patient. Instructions for the provider about how to fill out a form related to the mobility of the patient, or questions about mobility where no answer is given would fall into this category.

Example 1: Please record the patient's ability to perform the following activities: walking, Climbing, transferring, reaching.

Example 2: Does the patient have the ability to transfer from the bed to the chair?
Select Yes or No

7 EDGE OR DIFFICULT CASES

Below are some examples of mobility mentions and their annotations that could be challenging when applying the guidelines. These examples are not meant to be exhaustive but to offer some guidance in coding.

1. Her previous strategy had been to bring both of her LEs off the EOB while still supine and pivoting over her right elbow.
 - Mobility: The whole sentence.
 - type=subjective
 - subject=patient
 - timeline=past
 - Action: bring both of her LEs off the EOB
 - polarity=able
 - subdomain code=d410
 - Action: Supine
 - polarity=able
 - subdomain code=d415
2. Transitions sit-stand MI w/ verbal cues to push up from arms of chair versus pulling up on walker.
 - Mobility: The whole phrase.
 - type=objective
 - subject=patient
 - timeline=present
 - Action: Transition sit-stand
 - polarity=able
 - subdomain code=d410
 - Assistance : MI w/verbal Cues
 - polarity=true
 - source=person
 - Action: push
 - polarity=able
 - subdomain code=d445
 - Assistance: arms of chair
 - polarity=true
 - source=other
 - Action: pulling up
 - polarity=able
 - subdomain code=d445
 - Assistance: walker
 - polarity=false
 - source=device

2. **Able to move from sit on a raised surface to stand.**
 - Mobility: The whole phrase.
 - type=objective
 - subject=patient
 - timeline=present
 - Action: move from sit on a raised surface to stand.
 - polarity=able
 - subdomain code=d410
3. **I help her get up from bed and toilet and chair.**
 - Mobility: The whole sentence.
 - type=subjective
 - subject=patient
 - timeline=present
 - Action: get up from bed and toilet and chair
 - polarity=able
 - subdomain code=d410
 - Assistance: I help her
 - polarity=true
 - source=person

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APPENDIXES 1: ICF Mobility Codes and Definitions

Note: These ICF Mobility codes are the codes published and available on the ICF browser at the time the guideline was developed. The ICF continues to add codes to the online browser. ICF Mobility codes that are currently included in the ICF Browser that were not present at the time this guideline was developed include: d446 Fine foot use; d451 Going up and down stairs; d465 Moving around using equipment. We recommended users check the [ICF online browser](#) for the most updated classification and codes.

The table below displays ICF Mobility Codes and definitions with 3-digit parent codes and 4-digit child codes. Only the thirteen 3-digit Mobility codes listed below and bolded were used for annotation. The 4-digit child codes are displayed and defined for the benefit of the reader to provide greater conceptual clarity to the parent code.

ICF Mobility Codes and definitions		
Code	Name	Description
d410	Changing and maintaining body position	Getting into and out of a body position and moving from one location to another, such as getting up out of a chair to lie down on a bed, and getting into and out of positions of sitting, standing, kneeling, or squatting.
d4100	Lying down	Getting into and out of a lying down position or changing body position, from horizontal to any other position, such as standing up or sitting down.
d4101	Squatting	Getting into and out of the seated or crouched posture on one's haunches with knees closely drawn up or sitting on one's heels, such as may be necessary in toilets that are at floor level or changing body position from squatting to any other position, such as standing up.
d4102	Kneeling	Getting into and out of a position where the body is supported by the knees with legs bent, such as during prayers, or changing body position from kneeling to any other position, such as standing up.
d4103	Sitting	Getting into and out of a seated position and changing body position from sitting down to any other position, such as standing up or lying down.

ICF Mobility Codes and definitions		
Code	Name	Description
d4104	Standing	Getting into and out of a standing position or changing body position from standing to any other position, such as lying down or sitting down.
d4105	Bending	Tilting the back downwards or to the side, at the torso, such as in bowing or reaching down for an object.
d4106	Shifting the body's center of gravity	Adjusting or moving the weight of the body from one position to another while sitting, standing, or lying, such as moving from one foot to another while standing.
d4107	Rolling over	Moving the body from one position to another while lying such as turning from side to side or from stomach to back.
d415	Maintaining body position	Staying in the same body position as required, such as remaining seated or remaining standing for carrying out a task, in play, work or school.
	d4150 Maintaining a lying position	Staying in a lying position for some time as required, such as remaining in a prone position in a bed.
	d4151 Maintaining a squatting position	Staying in a squatting position such as when sitting on the floor without a seat.
	d4152 Maintaining a kneeling position	Staying in a kneeling position where the body is supported by the knees with legs bent for some time such as during prayers in church.
	d4153 Maintaining a sitting position	Staying in a seated position, on a seat or the floor, for some time such as when sitting at a desk or table.
	d4154 Maintaining a standing position	Staying in a standing position for some time such as when standing in a queue.

ICF Mobility Codes and definitions		
Code	Name	Description
	d4155 Maintaining head position	Controlling the position of the head and supporting its weight for a determined period.
d420	Transferring oneself	Moving from one surface to another, such as sliding along a bench or moving from a bed to a chair, without changing body position.
	d4200 Transferring oneself while sitting	Moving from a sitting position on one seat to another seat on the same or a different level, such as moving from a chair to a bed.
	d4201 Transferring oneself while lying	Moving from one lying position to another on the same or a different level, such as moving from one bed to another.
d430	Lifting and carrying objects	Raising up an object or taking something from one place to another, such as when lifting a cup or toy or carrying a box, or a child from one room to another.
	d4300 Lifting	Raising up an object to move it from a lower to a higher level, such as when lifting a glass from the table.
	d4301 Carrying in the hands	Taking or transporting an object from one place to another using the hands, such as when carrying a drinking glass or a suitcase.
	d4302 Carrying in the arms	Taking or transporting an object from one place to another using the arms and hands, such as when carrying a pet or a child or other large object.
	d4303 Carrying on shoulders, hip and back	Taking or transporting an object from one place to another using the shoulders, hip or back, or some combination of these, such as when carrying a large parcel or schoolbag.
	d4304 Carrying on the head	Taking or transporting an object from one place to another using the head, such when as carrying a container of water on the head.

ICF Mobility Codes and definitions		
Code	Name	Description
	d4305 Putting down objects	Using hands, arms, or other parts of the body to place an object down on a surface or place, such as when lowering a container of water to the ground.
d435	Moving objects with lower extremities	Performing coordinated actions aimed at moving an object by using the legs and feet, such as kicking a ball or pushing pedals on a bicycle.
	d4350 Pushing with lower extremities	Using the legs and feet to exert a force on an object to move it away, such as pushing a chair away with a foot.
	d4351 Kicking	Using the legs and feet to propel something away, such as kicking a ball.
d440	Fine hand use	Performing the coordinated actions of handling objects, picking up, manipulating and releasing them using one's hand, fingers and thumb, such as required to lift coins off a table or turn a dial or knob.
	d4400 Picking up	Lifting or taking up a small object with hands and fingers, such as when picking up a pencil.
	d4401 Grasping	Using one or both hands to seize and hold something, such as when grasping a tool or a doorknob.
	d4402 Manipulating	Using fingers and hands to exert control over, direct or guide something, such as when handling coins or other small objects, such as scissors, shoelaces, pencils, chop sticks, knives, and forks.
	d4403 Releasing	Using fingers and hands to let go or set free something so that it falls or changes position, such as when dropping an item of clothing or a piece of food for a pet.
d445	Hand and arm use	Performing the coordinated actions required to move objects or to manipulate them by using hands and arms, such as when turning door handles or throwing or catching an object.
	d4450 Pulling	Using fingers, hands, and arms to bring an object towards oneself, or to move it from place to place, such as when pulling on a string or pulling a door closed.

ICF Mobility Codes and definitions		
Code	Name	Description
	d4451 Pushing	Using fingers, hands, and arms to move something from oneself, or to move it from place to place, such as when pushing a toy or an animal away.
	d4452 Reaching	Using the hands and arms to extend outwards and touch and grasp something, such as when reaching across a table or desk for a book.
	d4453 Turning or twisting the hands or arms	Using fingers, hands, or arms to rotate, turn or bend an object, as is required to open a jar, or use tools such as toothbrush or screwdriver.
	d4454 Throwing	Using fingers, hands, and arms to lift something and propel it with some force through the air, such as when tossing a ball.
	d4455 Catching	Using fingers, hands, and arms to grasp a moving object in order to bring it to a stop and hold it, such as when catching a ball.
d450	Walking	Moving along a surface on foot, step by step, so that one foot is always on the ground, such as when strolling, sauntering, walking forwards, backwards, or sideways.
	d4500 Walking short distances	Walking for less than a kilometer, such as walking around rooms or hallways, within a building or for short distances outside.
	d4501 Walking long distances	Walking for more than a kilometer, such as across a village or town, between villages or across open areas.
	d4502 Walking on different surfaces	Walking on sloping, uneven, or moving surfaces, such as on grass, gravel or ice and snow, or walking aboard a ship, train, or other vehicle.
	d4503 Walking around obstacles	Walking in ways required to avoid moving and immobile objects, people, animals, and vehicles, such as walking around a marketplace or shop, around or through traffic or other crowded areas.
d455	Moving around	Moving the whole body from one place to another by means other than walking, such as climbing over a rock or running down a street, skipping, scampering, jumping, somersaulting, or running around obstacles.

ICF Mobility Codes and definitions		
Code	Name	Description
	d4550 Crawling	Moving the whole body in a prone position from one place to another on hands, or hands and arms, and knees.
	d4551 Climbing	Moving the whole body upwards or downwards, over surfaces or objects, such as climbing steps, rocks, ladders or stairs, curbs, or other objects.
	d4552 Running	Moving with quick steps so that both feet may be simultaneously off the ground.
	d4553 Jumping	Moving up off the ground by bending and extending the legs, such as jumping on one foot, hopping, skipping, and jumping or diving into water.
	d4554 Swimming	Propelling the whole body through water by means of limb and body movements without taking support from the ground underneath.
	d4555 Moving around while lying	Propelling the whole body from one place to another in a lying position without getting up.
	d4556 Moving around while sitting	Propelling the whole body from one place to another in a sitting position without getting up.
d460	Moving around in different locations	Walking and moving around in various places and situations, such as walking between rooms in a house, within a building, or down the street of a town.
	d4600 Moving around within the home	Walking and moving around in one's home, within a room, between rooms, and around the whole residence or living area.
	d4601 Moving around within buildings other than home	Walking and moving around within buildings other than one's residence, such as moving around other people's homes, other private buildings, community and public buildings and enclosed areas.
	d4602 Moving around outside	Walking and moving around close to or far from one's home and other buildings, without the use of transportation, public or

ICF Mobility Codes and definitions		
Code	Name	Description
	the home and other buildings	private, such as walking for short or long distances around a town or village.
d470	Using transportation	Using transportation to move around as a passenger, such as being driven in a car, bus, rickshaw, jitney, pram or stroller, wheelchair, animal-powered vehicle, private or public taxi, train, tram, subway, boat, or aircraft and using humans for transportation.
	d4700 Using human-powered vehicles	Being transported as a passenger by a mode of transportation powered by one or more people, such as riding in a pram or stroller, wheelchair propelled by another, rickshaw, or rowboat.
	d4701 Using private motorized transportation	Being transported as a passenger by private motorized vehicle over land, sea, or air, such as by car, taxi or privately owned aircraft or boat.
	d4703 Using humans for transportation	Being transported by another person, such as being carried in the arms, in a sheet, in a backpack or a transportation device.
d475	Driving	Being in control of and moving a vehicle or the animal that draws it, travelling under one's own direction or having at one's disposal any form of transportation appropriate for age, such as a car, bicycle, boat, or animal-powered vehicle.
	d4750 Driving human-powered transportation	Driving a human-powered vehicle, such as a bicycle, tricycle, or rowboat.
	d4751 Driving motorized vehicles	Driving a vehicle with a motor, such as an automobile, motorcycle, motorboat, or aircraft.
	d4752 Driving animal-powered vehicles	Driving a vehicle powered by an animal, such as a horse-drawn cart or carriage.

ICF Mobility Codes and definitions		
Code	Name	Description
d480	Riding animals for transportation	Travelling on the back of an animal, such as a horse, ox, camel, or elephant.

APPENDIX 2: Annotated Note for Mobility

Below is a synthetic physical therapy evaluation and discharge note that has been annotated for Mobility information according to the provided legend. Note that any information that resembles PII or PHI does not pertain to any real individual.

Legend:

Mobility mention

Action mention

Assistance mention

Quantification mention

Score definition mention

Instructions/Questions mention

PHYSICAL THERAPY EVALUATION AND DISCHARGE NOTE:

Name: Todd Finch
RMD Physician: Dr. Janet Hoffman
MRN: 1234567
DOB: 10/20/1954
Physical Therapist: Gerald Anderson PT

Date of Evaluation: 01/10/2024
Type of Visit: Outpatient visit
Reason for Referral: Weakness and balance issues associated with the progression of PD
Admitting Diagnosis: Parkinson's disease

PAST MEDICAL HISTORY:

Subjective Complaint: Mr. Finch is a 70-year-old male who was diagnosed with Parkinson's disease two year ago and was referred to NIH by his physician under protocol #1130-89-1234. Pt reports a h/o difficulty rising from a seated position and a fear of fall. Pt also reports he has difficulty when attempting to rise from the commode, and when walking on the sidewalk with uneven surfaces. Pt states that he has to remind himself to use his UEs during sit < > stand or when negotiating the stairs. To improve his mobility and balance, Mr. Finch received PT 3x/wk for 6 wks and his last appointment was 3 months ago. Pt reports that he still has some difficulty rising from a seated position but feels he is getting stronger since physical therapy. He describes stiffness and pain in his shoulder and LEs. This pain can be as severe as 7 on a 10 pt scale (where

0 = no pain and 10 = most severe). Pt reports that he takes Advil to control the pain when needed. Wife also states that approx. a month ago he **started having more difficulty walking**.

Social History/Level of function: Pt is married with two adult children aged 38 and 40 years old. He currently lives with his wife in a 3-level townhouse in Bethesda, Maryland. There are about 10 steps with one railing to enter the home. He used to play golf 2x a week but has recently stopped this exercise due to fatigue and shoulder/leg pain.

Past use of community services:

Outpatient rehab: Yes

Home health services: No

Prior level of function:

Difficulty with locomotion/movement (bed mobility, transfers, gait): Yes

Difficulty with self-care (bathing, dressing, eating, toileting): Yes

Difficulty with community and work activities/integration (work, school, recreation): Yes

Current Medications: Levodopa, carbidopa, and eldepryl

Other Relevant Clinical Tests: Reviewed in medical records.

Precautions: Fall risks

Patient's Goals: Remain as active and independent as possible.

OBJECTIVE:

Pt is alert and oriented to person, place, time and situation. He is able to follow commands with min difficulties. **NIHFA mobility score: 3/42 requires use of a walker for ambulation.**

[Mobility: Scoring: 1-4; 1=Total dependent 2= requires assistance of a person (with or without appliance), 3= requires appliances, orthosis or prosthesis for independence, 4= totally independent (indoors/outdoors)]

Seated examination reveals LE weakness in 4/5 range at hip flexors R > L and also 3+ at quads and hip abductors, distal strength is also slightly weaker on L for AT at 3+ but 4/5 on R. **With safety belt around waist, he can stand with min assist and appropriately place hands on walker.** He is **able to make slow deliberate automatic movements of forward walking with occasional cueing**. Commands are followed well but not entirely without flaws as processing appears to be slow. Simple and clear basic instructions are helpful. **Gait presents w/ decreased clearance of left foot during swing phase w/ 1 episode of foot drag and LOB noted during assessment but is able to recover w/ assistance;** mild circumduction and hip hike on right during swing face; self-selected pace. Pt states he is fatigued after **walking 10 feet with min assist** for cueing and balance. His affect is appropriate despite slow motor processing. He reports **moderate leg pain while walking**. Pt is **recommended standing or walking with hand support**.

ASSESSMENT:

Pt is a 70 y/o M w/ PD. He has moderate balance deficits on examination. He has weakness in his LEs on the L more so than the R and is **limited in community ambulation**. He is at high risk for falling due to balance deficits. He would benefit from education on fall prevention, as well as instruction in exercises to strengthen LEs and core. He would also benefit from continuing outpatient physical therapy in the community.

PLAN:

PT Treatment Plan/ Frequency and Duration of Care: This visit only

Patient Education: PT role, goals, recommendations for fall prevention in community and at home, HEP for LE and core strengthening (handouts provided)

PT Goals:

1. Assess patient's need for skilled physical therapy intervention and provide recommendations (GOAL MET)
2. Pt/family will verbalize/demonstrate understanding of education provided (GOAL MET)

Recommendations for post-episode of care: No additional skilled physical therapy indicated at this time. Pt was also encouraged to notify medical team if functional status declines.

Thank you for the opportunity to participate in this patient's care.

Electronic Signatures:

Gerald Anderson (PT) (Signed on 01/10/2024 15:00)

Authored

Last Updated: 01/10/2024 15:00 by Gerald Anderson (PT)

APPENDIX 3: Abbreviations found in clinical documentation

IN ACTION MENTIONS:

Amb = Ambulation

Bed mob = Bed mobility

EOB = Edge of bed

OOB = Out of bed

SLS = Single limb stance

SPT = Stand Pivot Transfer

STS = Sit to stand

Stair amb = Stair ambulation

t/f = transfer

IN ASSISTANCE MENTIONS:

a.d. = Assist device/ Assistive device

AD = Assistive device

AFO = Ankle foot orthosis

CGA = Contact guard assist

CG = Contact guard

FOS = flight of stairs

FO = Foot orthotic

FWW = Front wheeled walker

I = Independent

Ind = Independent

KAFO = Knee ankle foot orthosis

Lofstrand crutches = forearm crutches

LRAD = Less restrictive assistive device

MI = Modified independent
Max assist = Maximum assist/Maximal assist
Min A = Minimum assist/Minimal assist
Mod A = Moderate assist
Mod I = Modified Independence
PA = Physical assist
PFRW = platform rolling walker
Pt = Patient
PT = Physical therapist
PT = Physical therapy
QC = quad cane
R/W = Rolling walker/ Rollator walker
Rw = Rolling walker/ Rollator walker
S = Supervised/ Supervision
SBA = Stand by assist
SP cane = Single point cane
SPC = Single point cane
Sup = Supervised/ Supervision
Supv = Supervised/ Supervision
SPV = Supervision
VCs = Verbal cues/ Verbal command
W/C = Wheelchair

OTHERS:

act = activity
B = bilateral or bilaterally
b/i = bilateral

b/l = bilateral
BAMF = Brief Assessment of Motor Function
C/C = Chief or current complaint
dec = decline or declining
DLHR = Double leg heel raise
d/t = due to
EC = eyes closed
EO = eyes open
HAP = Human Activity Profile
HEP = Home Exercise Program
HR = heart rate
IEP = individualized Exercise Program
inc = incline
LEFS = Lower Extremity Functional Scale
LOB = loss of balance
LTG = long-term goal
MMT = Manual Muscle Test
NT = not tested
NWB = non-weight bearing
obs = observed
OT = occupational therapist or occupational therapy
PT = physical therapist or physical therapy
PPT = Physical Performance Test
PSFS = Patient Specific Functional Scale
PWB = partial weight bearing
QMA = Quantitative Muscle Assessment
STE = steps to entry or enter

STG = short-term goal

Ther ex = therapeutic exercise

TLSO = thoracolumbosacral orthosis

TTWB = Toe touch weight bearing

v/s = vital signs

WBAT = Weight bearing as tolerated

w/ = with

w/o = without

WHO = wrist/hand orthosis

WFL = Within Functional Limits

WNL = Within Normal Limits

APPENDIX 4: Troubleshooting Guide (Common terms and problems)

Action Entities:

Polarity: Able, Unclear, Unable

<u>ICF Code</u>	<u>Name</u>	<u>Example Action</u>
d410	Changing basic body position	Bed mobility, supine to sit, sit to supine, sit to stand (STS), squatting, lying down, kneeling, sitting, standing, bending, shifting the body's center of gravity, getting out of bed (OOB), rolling. Be careful to distinguish between changing and maintaining body position (ex. "Sitting" can be BOTH)
d415	Maintaining a body position	Sitting at the edge of bed (EOB), standing, maintaining a lying/squatting/kneeling/sitting/standing/body position, lying in the bed, single-limb stance (SLS) Be careful to distinguish between changing and maintaining body position (ex. "Squatting" can be BOTH)
d420	Transferring oneself	Bed to chair/wheelchair, transferring oneself while sitting/lying, transferring oneself, transfers, car transfers. Be careful to distinguish between changing body position and transferring oneself (Ex. "Moving from bed to chair" is d420, while "Transferring from bed to standing" is d410)
d430	Lifting and carrying objects	Loading/unloading (groceries), lifting, carrying in hands/arms, carrying on shoulders/hips/back/head, putting down objects, lifting and carrying
d435	Moving objects with lower extremities	Kicking (a ball), pushing (pedals), pushing with lower extremities
d440	Fine hand use	Using hands, fingers, and thumb for picking up, grasping, manipulating, releasing, handling (i.e., coins), turning knobs, etc.
d445	Hand and arm use	Pulling, pushing, reaching, turning or twisting the hands or arms, throwing, catching
d450	Walking	Ambulating, walking, ambulating on the unit, ambulating around the room, ambulating in the hallway
d455	Moving around	Climbing the stairs, running, swimming, crawling, jumping, stairs* (with implied action), ascend/descend stairs
d460	Moving around in different locations	Walking to the bathroom, moving around within the home, moving around or within buildings/facilities, moving from place to place, community ambulation, ambulating around the unit,

		<p>ambulating around, ambulating within the room, ambulating in the room.</p> <p>Be careful to distinguish between moving around (d450) and moving around in different locations (d460). When an action mentions a location then it is likely d460.</p>
d470	Using transportation	Riding the bus, taking the metro, being transported in a wheelchair propelled by another, being transported as a passenger in a vehicle,
d475	Driving	Riding a bike, driving a car, commuting by car
d480	Riding animals for transportation	Riding a horse
NO CODE		<p>Scotting, propelling wheelchair, wheelchair mobility, propulsion, traversing, negotiating, marching, marching in place, getting around, managing, transporting (someone in a wheelchair or wheelchair transport), positioning, stairs negotiation.</p> <p>Assign “no code” as the subdomain code when <u>a single verb describes two actions</u> that correspond to different ICF codes [ex. “Patient ambulated in the hallway (d450) and the stairs (d455).”]</p>
EXCLUSION		Arm swings, exercises (calf raises, heel slides, supine bridging, LE strengthening), balance, entering the house, nursing goals, trunk twisting, ROM, ADL, overhead activity, positioning, nursing goals

*The word “stairs” when found in Mobility mentions can refer to climbing (e.g., “difficulty with stairs”). In cases like this, we need to consider colloquial language.

Assistance Entities

Polarity: True (dependent), False (independent), or Unclear. Future mentions of assistance have no Polarity.

Source: Device Only, Person Only, or Other

DEVICE ONLY	Canes, crutches, long-handled reachers, walkers, “modified independence,” and wheelchairs
PERSON ONLY	“Total assist,” “maximal assist,” “moderate assist,” “minimal assist,” “contact guard assist,” “supervision”, and “verbal cues.”
OTHER	IV pole, handrail, brace/orthotics, counter, furniture, bed control (used by patient), adaptive devices (e.g., elevated/raised head of bed, raised toilet seats, frame of bed), prosthetic devices, arms of chair.
NOT INCLUDED	Assistance from upper extremities

Common Problems: (With page references in Mobility Guideline)

1. **Assistance vs. Assist** (Page 28-29)
 - When an individual requires “assistance,” with no further details, the source of the assistance is “no source” as it is unknown if the assist refers to a person or device.
 - When the text states “min-max assist” code the source as Person
2. **Independent** (Page 28)
 - When “independent” refers to a source (device, person, or other), the polarity is false, and the appropriate source is selected.
 - If “independent” does not refer explicitly specify a source, assign “no source” as the source.
3. **Gait** (Page 27)
 - Assign a subdomain code d450 for gait but leave its polarity as “no polarity.”
4. **With/without** (Page 29-30)
 - Do include with/without for assistance entities, but do not include with/without for action mentions.
5. **Modifying words – uses / requires / is able to / maintains / demonstrates**
 - **Assistance Entities:** Include modifying words when in the past or present, but do not include when in the future. (Ex. Do include “uses” in “uses walker” when in the past or present but exclude “use” in “use walker” when in the future.)
 - **Action Entities:** If a verb is vital to an action mention (modifies its meaning) then include it in the action mention. (Ex. “Patient maintains standing x 3 minutes”). Do not include modifying words that are already implied by the polarity of the entity. (Ex. “Patient was able to walk for half an hour.” Do not include performance qualifiers such as “able to” or “unable to” or “impossible” in the action mention).
6. **Difficulty / Impaired / Decreased** (Page 14, and 25)
 - The polarity of an action is unclear if the medical record notes that the patient has “difficulty with...,” “Impaired...,” or “decreased...”
7. **Exercises vs. Education**
 - Exercises are excluded from mobility mentions. (Ex. “Patient was able to perform DLHR.”)
 - Education is included in mobility mentions (Ex. “Patient given instructions in gait training.”), but the polarity of the action/assistance mentions is assigned as “no polarity.”
 - Recommendations on the mobility of patient to nursing and other staff are coded as “Other.”
8. **Moving around using equipment**
 - If an individual is described as moving around using equipment, then the equipment is not included in the action mention. (Ex. “Patient uses wheelchair to

move to the living room” – this is not an action mention; instead “wheelchair” would be annotated as an assistance entity).

9. Headers, titles, and generic programs (Page 22)

- Only annotate headers when there is no action-related information in the following text. (“*Ambulation: independent*” – whole phrase is captured in mobility mention).
- Do not annotate headers when the following text contains action-related information. (Ex. “*Gait pattern: abnormal gait.*” – only “abnormal gait” would be captured in the mobility mention).

10. Patient Goals vs. PT Goals

- When capturing a goal as a mobility mention, patient goals are subjective and PT goals are always objective.

11. Not Assessed / Not Tested (Page 20)

- If a medical record labels functional status as “*not assessed/tested (NT)*,” then capture it as a mobility mention and annotate any sub-mentions without a polarity attribute.

12. Owning Equipment / Environmental Factors

- Do not annotate assistance mentions when talking about something that the patient owns or has at home (e.g., The patient has a rolling walker at home), this is NOT an assistance mention as the patient is not using them.

13. Walking/Ambulating Around/On Unit/In Room/etc.

- d450 = Walking, ambulating.
- d460 = Ambulating around the unit, ambulating around, ambulating within the room, ambulating in the room.

14. Fit with / Instructed in use / Sent home with / Issued...

- If patient is “*fit with*” or “*sent home with*” an assistive device, then that does not count as an assistance mention.
- If patient is “*Instructed in use*” of an assistive device, then that does count as an assistance mention with no polarity.